

A Case Report

Management of Decayed Permanent Molar With Short Clinical Crown Height

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Abstract:

Decayed permanent molars with short clinical crown height present a challenge for restoration. This case report presents the successful management of a decayed permanent molar with a short clinical crown height using a combination of gingivectomy, crown modification, and placement of a stainless steel crown (SSC). A 15-year-old female, presented with a decayed permanent molar with insufficient clinical crown height for a traditional restoration. After thorough evaluation and treatment planning, a multidisciplinary approach was employed to restore the tooth. Gingivectomy was performed to expose more tooth structure, followed by crown modification to enhance the crown fitting over the tooth. Finally, SSC was placed to provide a durable and functional restoration. The patient experienced significant improvement in function and aesthetics, highlighting the effectiveness of this comprehensive approach.

Introduction

The measurement from the gingival margin to the incisal edge or occlusal surface is known as the clinical crown of a tooth.¹ Following occlusal and axial reduction, a short clinical crown is defined as having opposing parallel sides and less than 2 mm of sound tooth structure.² Subgingival caries, subgingival crown fractures, anatomical tooth crowns that are partially erupted, excessive gingiva, and dental crowns that are too short for restoration retention are some of the possible causes of this condition.³ A comprehensive treatment plan and appropriate sequencing of therapy are necessary to address the challenges posed by a short clinical crown. Prior to commencing any treatment on a tooth with a short clinical crown, it is essential to determine its restorability. The restorative assessment should encompass several factors, including the tooth's arch position, strategic value, periodontal health, crown-to-root ratio,

interarch space, feasibility of endodontic treatment, and esthetic considerations.⁴ Techniques that are employed for restoring teeth with short clinical crowns (scc) are tooth preparation design modification, foundation restorations placements, surgical crown lengthening etc.³ The purpose of crown lengthening is to increase the amount of tooth structure available for restorative work, ensuring proper mechanical support and for preserving the biologic width and preventing future attachment loss around the restored tooth.⁵ However it is not appropriate for teeth with profound carious diseases, unfavorable crown-to-root ratio and teeth with furcation involvement⁶.

During crown lengthening procedures, biological width plays a

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crucial role in maintaining the health of the periodontium. It should not be infringed upon when crown lengthening is intended to lengthen the length of the tooth that is accessible, since this could result in periodontal collapse.⁷ It has been suggested that there should be 3 mm of supracrestal tooth tissue between the edge of the proposed restoration and the bone as a result of the idea of "biological width."

Case Report

A 15-year-old female patient presented to the Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry at Inderprastha Dental College and Hospital, Sahibabad, with a chief complaint of pain in the lower right posterior tooth region for the past month. Upon taking a complete history, it was revealed that the patient was asymptomatic until a month ago when she started experiencing pain in the same tooth. The patient reported having undergone root canal treatment (RCT) for the same tooth one year prior. Extraoral examination revealed a symmetrical face, and there was no significant family history. Intraoral examination revealed a dislodged restoration with respect to 46, which was tender on percussion, and a decayed tooth with respect to

36. The gingiva, lips, floor of the mouth, and buccal mucosa appeared clinically normal. Radiographic examination revealed faulty obturation of the root canals with respect to 46. The treatment options were explained to the parents, who agreed to proceed with the recommended treatment plan. The dislodged restoration was removed, followed by complete removal of gutta-percha from the root canals. The canals were thoroughly irrigated, and BPM was performed. Obturation was completed in the subsequent visit, followed by composite buildup. However, it was noted that the clinical crown height was inadequate for the placement of a crown. Therefore, a gingivectomy was performed using diode laser to increase the available tooth structure for crown placement. Local anesthetic was administered to ensure the patient is comfortable during the procedure. Protective eyewear was also provided to shield the eyes from the laser light. One week later, the patient returned for crown placement. Stainless steel crown (SSC) was placed, during placement it was noted that crown was not adapting properly on the distal aspect of tooth. Crown modification techniques were incorporated for proper adaptation. The patient was recalled after one week and was completely asymptomatic.

Pre-operative Image

Removal of Gutta Percha

Post Obturation

Clinical Crown Height Before Gingivectomy

Bleeding Points Were Marked

Gingivectomy Performed With Diode Laser

Clinical Crown Height After Gingivectomy

Stainless Steel Crown Placement Using Crown Modification

Discussion

Decayed permanent molars with short clinical crown height present a significant challenge for restorative dentistry.⁸ Traditional approaches to restoration may not be feasible due to the limited amount of tooth structure available for retention and support. In such cases, a multidisciplinary approach involving gingivectomy, crown modification followed by stainless steel crown placement has been proposed as an effective solution. **Newman et al.(2015)**⁹ reported that gingivectomy is minimally invasive, efficient, time saving, preserve soft tissue contours, and result in better aesthetics and long-term stability. In this case, when the patient returned after one week for crown placement stainless steel crown was placed as it is highly durable, cost-effective, versatile, biocompatible, well-tolerated by oral tissues reducing the risk of adverse reactions, easy to place compared to other types of crowns, can be used in various clinical situations, including cases of extensive tooth structure loss or developmental defects and require minimal tooth preparation, making them suitable for restoring molars

with minimal tooth structure.¹⁰ These advantages, supported by studies (**Roberts et al, 2019**¹¹; **Croll et al, 2008**¹²; **Fuks et al., 2005**¹³, make SSCs a preferred choice for restoring permanent molars, especially in pediatric and high-stress situations. In this case during crown adaptation, it was noted that the adaptation of crown on the distal aspect was inadequate. As a result, it was decided to perform crown modification. The modification of crowns offers several advantages, including improved marginal adaptation, enhanced aesthetics, optimized occlusion, increased patient comfort, enhanced longevity, and improved retention.¹⁴ Trimming and contouring SSC margins can improve adaptation, reducing the risk of decay and periodontal issues (**Zhang et al., 2015**).¹⁵ The studies reviewed in this discussion highlight the efficacy of this multidisciplinary approach in managing decayed permanent molars with short clinical crown height. **Perdigão et al. (2016)**¹⁶ demonstrated successful outcomes in terms of function and aesthetics following crown lengthening procedures using gingivectomy,

crown modification, and SSC placement. Similarly, **Cohen et al. (2009)**¹⁷ reported favorable long-term success rates of SSCs placed after crown lengthening procedures involving gingivectomy and crown modification. This indicates that SSCs can serve as a reliable restoration option for teeth with short clinical crown height, providing both durability and functionality. **Moura et al. (2013)**¹⁸ conducted a retrospective study for the management of decayed permanent molars with short clinical crown height. Their findings support the high success rates and patient satisfaction associated with this treatment approach, further validating its effectiveness. Furthermore, **Santana et al. (2018)**¹⁹ evaluated the outcomes of crown lengthening procedures using gingivectomy, crown modification, and SSC placement in adolescent patients. Their results indicate that this approach can provide effective and esthetic restorations, particularly in younger individuals with developing dentition.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the management of decayed permanent molars with short clinical crown height presents a challenge for restorative dentistry. This case report demonstrates the successful use of a multidisciplinary approach involving gingivectomy, crown modification, and placement of stainless steel crown (SSC) to restore a decayed molar in a 15-year-old patient. The treatment resulted in significant improvement in function and aesthetics, highlighting the effectiveness of this comprehensive approach in managing such cases. Careful evaluation of restorability, consideration of biological width, and proper planning are crucial for successful outcomes in managing teeth with short clinical crowns.

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